

NON-GEODESIC WINDING EQUATIONS
ON A GENERAL SURFACE OF REVOLUTION

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ABSTRACT

The non-geodesic filament winding is the process in which the friction between the resin impregnated filament and the bases is utilized in order to prevent any slippage between them. Based on the stable condition and concept about normal curvature, geodesic curvature and Liouville's equation in Differential Geometry, non-geodesic stable winding condition on a general surface of revolution is presented in this paper. Calculation formulas and numerical solution of the non-geodesic winding on these surface were given in this paper.

INTRODUCTION

The filament winding of composite materials is widely used for making rocket generators and pressure vessels along with vigorous development of science and technology. The filament must be accurately, stably wound on a core barrel and a end closure in order to obtain the products possessed of light-weight, high specific strength and rigidity. Based on winding process, a geodesic winding on a curved surface is ideal slidless winding. It is basis for calculating regularity wound filament, designing and controlling movement of the fiber feed arm. However, because the shape of a filament winding product is becoming more complex, the situations which do not satisfy the condition for geodesic winding are more and more.

In recent years, many scholars have been studying the subject of non-geodesic winding on the surface of revolution.

Non-geodesic stable winding condition is presented in the article [1], but applicable equation to engineering isn't directly presented. Approximate applicable formulas obtained by static analysis are presented in the articles [2-3]. Non-geodesic winding equations on a general surface of revolution, which can be obtained with the use of Differential Geometry, are presented in the article [4], but used method is complex. In this paper, the lines net of curvature of the curved surface should be curve net of selected parameters. Based on the normal curvature and the geodesic curvature and Liouville's equation in Differential Geometry, non-geodesic stable winding condition on a general surface is studied and non-geodesic stable winding equations on the often used surface of revolution in the engineering are presented, their approximate solutions can be obtained with Runge-Kutta method.

EQUATIONS OF EQUILIBRIUM

In order to prevent any slippage of the filament, the friction between the filament and the base is utilized. At the point P of the filament two forces have to be considered: the normal force F_n and the sideways force F_s . The following relationship exists between them: $\beta = \text{tg}^{-1} (F_s / F_n)$.

If slippage of the filament is to be prevented then,

$$\beta \leq \varphi \tag{1}$$

where φ is friction angle, as shown in Fig.1.

According to the Ref.[1], $\beta = \text{tg}^{-1} (K_g / K_n)$, then

$$K_g / K_n \leq \mu \tag{2}$$

is the condition of equilibrium for realizing non-geodesic stable winding (μ is the coefficient of friction).

Figure 1

Figure 2

The equation of a general surface of revolution

Designating a curve in the plane XOZ for rotating **around** the axis Z, the surface of revolution can be obtained and its equation is $\vec{r}(u,v) = \{ f(v)\cos u, f(v)\sin u, g(v) \}$ (3)

where $0 \leq u \leq 2\pi, a \leq v \leq b$, curve u is called to latitude and curve v is called to meridian, as shown in Fig.2.

On the surface $\vec{r}(u,v)$, a filament path curve C through any point P has: $u=u(s), v=v(s)$. The normal curvature K_n of the curve C at the point P is :

$$K_n = \frac{Ldu^2 + 2Mdudv + Ndv^2}{Edu^2 + 2Fdudv + Gdv^2} \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{where } r_u &= \{-f\sin u, f\cos u, 0\} & r_v &= \{f'\cos u, f'\sin u, g'\} \\ r_{uu} &= \{-f\cos u, -f\sin u, 0\} & r_{vv} &= \{f''\cos u, f''\sin u, g''\} \\ r_{uv} &= \{-f'\sin u, f'\cos u, 0\} \\ E &= f^2, & F &= 0, & G &= f'^2 + g'^2 \\ L &= -fg' / (f'^2 + g'^2)^{3/2}, & M &= 0, & N &= (g'f'' - f'g'') / G^{3/2}. \end{aligned}$$

As mentioned previously, taking the orthogonal curve net as parametric curve net in which curves u are perpendicular to curves v, the unit tangent vector \vec{T} tangential to the curve C at P may be expressed by means of $\vec{e}_1 = r_u / E^{1/2}, \vec{e}_2 = r_v / G^{1/2}$. Designing the direction angle between \vec{e}_1 and \vec{T} as τ , the direction angle from \vec{T} to \vec{e}_2 as α , according to define, α is winding angle and $\alpha + \tau = \pi/2$.

Based on Liouville's equation, the geodesic curvature K_g at the point P is :

$$K_g = \frac{d\tau}{ds} - \frac{1}{2G^{1/2}} \frac{\partial \ln E}{\partial v} \cos \tau + \frac{1}{2E^{1/2}} \frac{\partial \ln G}{\partial u} \sin \tau \quad (5)$$

2. Filament stable winding equation on the surface

After some transforming, We get fibre stable winding equation on the surface :

$$\frac{d\alpha}{du} = - \frac{\mu \cos^2 \alpha [-g'(f'^2 + g'^2) \operatorname{tg}^2 \alpha + g'ff'' - ff'g'']}{\sin \alpha (f'^2 + g'^2)^{3/2}} - \frac{f'}{(f'^2 + g'^2)^{1/2}} \quad (6)$$

or

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dv} = - \frac{1}{f \cos \alpha} \left\{ \frac{\mu [-g'(f'^2 + g'^2) \operatorname{tg}^2 \alpha + g'ff'' - ff'g''] \cos^2 \alpha}{(f'^2 + g'^2)} - f' \cos \alpha \right\}$$

THE FIBRE STABLE WINDING EQUATIONS ON A OFT-USED SURFACE OF REVOLUTION. AND THEIR NUMERICAL SOLUTION

For the convenient of utilization in engineering, the fibre stable winding equations on a oft-used surface of revolution are presented in this paper. The equations were solved by means of Runge-Kutta method as follows:

1. Cylindrical

Designating a curve in the plane XOZ L: $\begin{cases} X=f(v)=R \\ Z=g(v)=Rtg\varphi \end{cases} \quad u=\theta,$
 (where $0 \leq \varphi \leq \pi/2, 0 \leq \theta = 2\pi$)

for rotating around the axis Z, the cylindrical surface can be obtained (as shown in Fig.3). Non-geodesic stable winding

equation on the surface is:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{d\theta} = \mu \sin \alpha \tag{7}$$

$$\text{or} \quad \frac{d\alpha}{d\varphi} = \frac{\mu \sin^2 \alpha}{\cos \alpha \cos^2 \varphi}$$

Figure 3

It is known from Fig.4 that :

- (1) The winding angle α is progressive incremental function of θ . The bigger increasing the initial winding angle α_0 , winding angle α changes to 90° the faster along with the smaller corresponding running angle θ and the shorter the length of non-geodesic winding.
- (2) Effect of μ on the α - θ curve is stronger. As increasing μ , gradient of α changes large and α arrives to 90° fastly, then corresponding running angle θ is small and the length of non-geodesic winding also is shorter.

Figure 4

2. Conical

Designating a curve in the plane XOZ $L: \begin{cases} X=f(v)=R-Ztg\varphi_0 \\ Z=g(v)=Z \end{cases}$

$u=\theta$ ($0 < \varphi_0 < \pi/2, 0 \leq \theta = 2\pi$) for rotating around the axis Z, the conical surface can be obtained (as shown in Fig.5).

Non-geodesic stable winding equation on the surface is :

$$\frac{d\alpha}{d\theta} = \mu \sin\alpha \cos\varphi_0 + \sin\varphi_0 \quad (8)$$

or

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dz} = \frac{tg\alpha}{R-Ztg\varphi_0} (\mu \sin\alpha + tg\varphi_0)$$

Figure 5

It is observed from Fig.6:

(1) Along with increasing the initial winding angle α_0 , winding angle α easily changes to 90° and corresponding running angle θ is even more small, the length Z of non-geodesic winding is shorter. Compared with non-geodesic winding on cylindrical surface, influence of α_0 is more notable and incremental with increment of the angle φ_0 .

(2) The bigger the coefficient of friction μ , winding angle α changes to 90° the faster along with the smaller corresponding running angle θ and the length of non-geodesic winding the shorter. Effect of μ on the shape of the $\alpha-\theta$ curve and the Z- θ curve is stronger.

Figure 6

3. Spherical

The parametric equation of the spherical surface is presented as following:

$$\vec{r}(u, v) = \{ R \sin \varphi \cos \theta, R \sin \varphi \sin \theta, R \cos \varphi \}$$

where $0 \leq \varphi \leq \pi, 0 \leq \theta \leq 2\pi$, as shown in Fig.7.

Figure 7

Non-geodesic stable winding equation on the surface is :

$$\frac{d\alpha}{d\theta} = -\frac{\mu \sin \varphi}{\sin \alpha} - \cos \varphi \tag{9}$$

or

$$\frac{d\alpha}{d\varphi} = \frac{\mu + \text{ctg} \varphi \sin \alpha}{\cos \alpha}$$

In the case of Fig.8, it is seen that

(1) There is some difference in winding angle α among various point on the spherical surface, α is the function of θ . The smaller the initial winding angle α_0 , winding angle α changes the bigger within the limits of change θ from 0° to 360° and the region of non-geodesic winding is the bigger.

Correspondingly, the α_0 is even the bigger, then that means the winding path is approaching to the equatorial circle and the region of non-geodesic winding is the smaller.

(2) Along with increasing μ , the $\alpha - \theta$ curves become more gently and the resion of non-geodesic winding is the bigger.

Figure 8

4. Oblate ellipsoidal surface

The parametric equation of the oblate ellipsoidal surface is :

$$\vec{r}(u, v) = \{ a \cos \varphi \cos \theta, a \cos \varphi \sin \theta, b \sin \varphi \}$$

where $0 < b < a;$
 $-\pi/2 < \varphi < \pi/2;$
 $0 \leq \theta \leq 2\pi.$

(as shown in Fig.9)

Figure 9

Non-geodesic winding equation on the oblate ellipsoidal surface is :

$$\frac{d\alpha}{d\theta} = \frac{\mu b \cos \varphi \cos^2 \alpha [(a^2 \sin^2 \varphi + b^2 \cos^2 \varphi) \operatorname{tg}^2 \alpha + a^2]}{\sin \alpha (a^2 \sin^2 \varphi + b^2 \cos^2 \varphi)^{3/2}} + \frac{a \sin \varphi}{(a^2 \sin^2 \varphi + b^2 \cos^2 \varphi)^{1/2}} \quad (10)$$

or

$$\frac{d\alpha}{d\varphi} = \frac{\mu b \cos \alpha [(a^2 \sin^2 \varphi + b^2 \cos^2 \varphi) \operatorname{tg}^2 \alpha + a^2]}{a(a^2 \sin^2 \varphi + b^2 \cos^2 \varphi)} + \operatorname{tg} \alpha \operatorname{tg} \varphi$$

From Fig.10 ,it is known

- (1) The smaller the α_0 , the changing gradient of the $\alpha-\theta$ curves changes large and the length of non-geodesic winding is the bigger.
- (2) The bigger the μ , change of the α is stronger, but the region of non-geodesic winding changes very small. The endclosure of pressure vessels often is oblate ellipsoidal surface with different open end. Selecting adaptable α_0 and regulating μ , it is possible to realize given non-geodesic stable winding.

Figure 10

5. Paraboloid of revolution

The parametric equation of the paraboloid surface of revolution is presented as following :

$$\vec{r}(u, v) = \{ r \cos \theta, r \sin \theta, r^2 / (2P) \}$$

where $0 \leq \theta \leq 2\pi$, $0 < r$, as shown in Fig.11.

Figure 11

It is observed from Fig.12 :

- (1) α is the progressive decrement function of θ . The bigger the initial winding angle α_0 , the decrement gradient changes

large and along with change of θ , α is tended towards constant value (approximate to 3°) for different initial winding angle α_0 .

X is the progressive increment function of θ . The smaller the α_0 , the increment gradient of X changes the bigger and along with the smaller corresponding running angle θ .

(2) Effect of μ on the α - θ curve is stronger. When μ is small, α is the progressive decrement function of θ . As μ is more bigger, the α - θ curve changes into saddle curve and the corresponding X - θ curve changes very slowly. For this reason, if this surface needs to be adopted, it is suggested that to try to keep the bigger μ .

Figure 12

CONCLUSION

1. The non-geodesic winding equation on the general and the oft-used surfaces of revolution were presented in this paper, it provided a basis for determining winding regularity, controlling motion of the fibre feed arm and calculating construction strength and rigidity of the products.
2. The non-geodesic winding equations on the cylindrical and conical surface obtained in this paper are somewhat similar to the Ref.[3], and they have the more advantage of far and wide adaptability for the calculation on the computer and the winding with computer controlling than Ref.[3].

3. In the general engineering, the necessarily wound structures may be simple surface above discussed or their combination. Therefore the formulas and analysis about the influence of the initial winding angle α_0 , coefficient of friction μ on the winding path presented in this paper may become basic for solving a problem in engineering and go far toward optimizing design.

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